

CHARACTERISTICS OF HEARING IMPAIRMENT IN ADULT PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC KIDNEY DISEASE NOT ON DIALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

Hearing loss affects nearly 1.6 billion people and is the third leading cause of disability worldwide [1]. Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is also a common condition associated with adverse clinical outcomes and high healthcare costs [2]. Various mechanisms have been proposed for the development of hearing loss in people with CKD.

Introduction. Hearing loss affects nearly 1.6 billion people and is the third leading cause of disability worldwide [1]. Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is also a common condition associated with adverse clinical outcomes and high healthcare costs [2]. Various mechanisms have been proposed for the development of hearing loss in people with CKD. The kidneys and the inner ear share many functional and structural similarities, which may contribute to these problems in patients with CKD [3]. Furthermore, changes in water and electrolyte homeostasis can affect endolymphatic fluid, leading to endolymphatic hydrops [4]. Finally, certain medications, such as aminoglycosides and loop diuretics, are well known for their ototoxicity and are used to treat patients with CKD [5]. To date, only a small number of population-based studies have demonstrated a link between CKD and audiovestibular disorders [6–8].

Objective. The aim of the study was to investigate the association between chronic kidney disease and sensorineural hearing loss in adult patients not receiving dialysis and without diabetes mellitus, and to characterize the audiological features and functional state of the auditory system in this patient population.

Materials and Methods. Patients aged 18 to 60 years with chronic kidney disease, without diabetes mellitus, and without a personal history of otological diseases were compared with a healthy control group matched for age and gender to identify differences in their audiological profiles.

Results. The study included 51 cases, the results of which were compared with data from 51 healthy volunteers. The audiometric profile identified in patients with chronic kidney disease included sensorineural hearing loss in the frequency range from 4 to 8 kHz based on hearing threshold audiometry (HTA), decreased reproducibility of delayed evoked otoacoustic emissions (DEOAE), and decreased otoacoustic emissions at the frequency of the distortion product (DPOAE). Increases in absolute V-wave latency and III-V and I-V interwave latencies were also found in auditory brainstem evoked potentials (ABRs), but within normal limits.

Conclusion. There is a correlation between chronic kidney disease in adult patients not on dialysis and without diabetes and sensorineural hearing loss affecting high frequencies and with the cochlea as the primary site of hearing damage. The relationship between these two common conditions is not always obvious, but it has important implications for research and clinical practice.

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